

Asset Structure and Market Value of Quoted Consumer Goods Companies in Nigeria

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Abstract

Assets are essential resources for quoted companies for the purpose of generating revenue. Managers of public companies are expected to acquire and accumulate these assets in such a way that profits as well as shareholders' wealth are maximized. Quoted consumer goods companies in Nigeria are not excluded, as assets are used in conducting business activities. Thus, it is important to assess the influence of asset structure on the market value of these entities. This study was conducted to examine the influence of asset structure on the market value of quoted consumer goods companies in Nigeria from 2013 to 2022. The ex-post facto research design was employed in the study. There were twenty-one (21) consumer goods companies on the floor of the Nigerian Exchange Group (NGX) as of December 2022. The census sampling method was adopted, as the twenty-one (21) entities were studied on the basis of availability of data in accordance with the variables of the study. The dependent variable was Market Value (MV), while the independent variable was Asset Structure (AS), measured by Tangible Assets (TANG), Intangible Assets (ITA), and Current Assets (CA). Panel data were collected from annual reports and financial statements of the sampled entities from 2013 to 2022. The data were analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics. A fixed-effect linear regression technique was used in the study. From the analyses, it was revealed that TANG,

ITA, and CA had positive and significant influence on MCAP of quoted consumer goods companies in Nigeria (TANG, $\beta=3.9465$, $t\text{-stat}=13.488$, $p\text{-value}=0.0000$, $Adjusted R^2=0.7924$; ITA, $\beta=5.7252$, $t\text{-stat}=3.5569$, $p\text{-value}=0.0005$, $Adjusted R^2=0.5512$; CA, $\beta=3.8290$, $t\text{-stat}=3.5334$, $p\text{-value}=0.0006$, $Adjusted R^2=0.5507$). It was concluded that intangible assets exerted the highest influence on the market value of quoted consumer goods companies in Nigeria. It was recommended that adequate investment and effective management should be done on the key variables of asset structure, such as tangible, intangible, and current assets, for the purpose of increasing market value of those entities in Nigeria.

Keywords: asset structure, market value, tangible assets, intangible assets, panel data regression

Introduction

Investments of quoted companies in the 21st century are mostly done through the acquisition of non-current assets such as buildings, land, and other properties and the maintenance of liquidity positions. This is because assets are the foundation of revenue generation and the profit maximization of quoted companies. The structure of assets could affect the level of revenue to be generated as well as the profits of the companies positively or negatively. On this note, management of companies has realized the importance of deciding on the appropriateness of the kind of assets to acquire and the level of investments to be made in current assets to maintain a high reputation of honoring obligations when they fall due, as illiquidity could reduce the reputation of quoted companies.

Assets are recognized as the base from which other accounting attributes are influenced, and an improper combination of those assets could affect other accounting attributes negatively, which could in turn impact the market value of the company negatively. Asset structure could be described as the possible combination of different types of assets by managers of quoted companies based on their decisions in different accounting periods. The basic classification of assets, as recognized by international accounting standards, includes non-current assets and current assets (Inyama et al., 2017). Non-current assets are subdivided into tangible and intangible assets. To achieve maximum market value and to improve the wealth of shareholders of quoted companies, managers must be able to strike a balance between asset compositions that could influence the indicators of shareholders' wealth, such as stock price, profits, and total equity. This is because acquiring and

accumulating certain assets can help a company generate more revenue, which in turn can increase profitability and strengthen its equity position.

When all these accounting attributes are optimized through the appropriate combination of assets, the market value of the company could be maximized. Market value is described as the level of improvement in all the indicators of shareholders' investments or wealth, which includes stock price and dividends. Market value could be measured by stock price, market capitalization, price-earnings (P/E) ratio, the model of Tobin's Q, price-to-book ratio, and market value of equity (Sinha, 2017).

Most existing studies have focused on financial performance, so market value receives little attention from researchers. In the quoted consumer goods companies in Nigeria, studies on asset structure and market value received little attention, as even assets are viewed by scholars as fundamental resources of modern organization. It is on this note that the study was considered essential to address the critical issues in the literature, particularly from the period of 2013 to 2022.

Statement of the Problem

An understanding of the relationship between asset structure and market value of companies is an important aspect of studies in modern times because of the role of assets in the growth of organizations. When a quoted company generates lower revenue in an accounting period, the first thing to look at is the total assets used to generate such revenue. When a company makes less profit or loss, it is the total assets used in the operation that will be considered before any other factor. Managers of modern, quoted companies have not fully appreciated the importance of asset structure in sustaining company growth over different accounting periods. For instance, in some quoted companies in Nigeria, it could be observed that larger non-current assets are accumulated but little and no profit is made in the accounting period, and this situation usually exerts a negative effect on the wealth of the shareholders.

However, there is a need for managers of quoted companies to appropriately decide on the kind of assets to invest available funds in for the purpose of maximizing the market value of their companies, as the acquisition of assets that are not properly decided by the management based on the stream of revenue expected may in turn affect the growth of the entities. Previous studies on asset structure are mainly on the financial performance of companies measured by the ratios of profitability and firm value measured by the model of Tobin's Q (Nyamasege et al., 2014; Setiadharna & Machali, 2017; Adebimpe & Umoh, 2026). The market value of quoted companies in an empirical study of asset structure is rarely measured by market capitalization, which could provide different empirical findings. Also, asset

structure in previous studies was mainly represented by non-current assets and current assets with limited attention on intangible assets, which could also influence the market value of quoted companies (Charlie & Edet, 2023). Hence, there is need for the study.

Objectives of the Study

The main objective of the study was to assess the influence of asset structure on the market value of quoted consumer goods companies in Nigeria. The specific objectives of the study were to:

- i. Determine the influence of tangible assets on market capitalization of quoted consumer goods companies in Nigeria.
- ii. Ascertain the influence of intangible assets on market capitalization of quoted consumer goods companies in Nigeria.
- iii. Examine the influence of current assets on market capitalization of quoted consumer goods companies in Nigeria.
- iv. Examine the combined influence of tangible assets, intangible assets, and current assets on the market capitalization of quoted consumer goods companies in Nigeria.

Research Questions

The following research questions were raised from the objectives of the study:

- i. What is the influence of tangible assets on market capitalization of quoted consumer goods companies in Nigeria?
- ii. How do intangible assets affect the market capitalization of quoted consumer goods companies in Nigeria?
- iii. What is the influence of current assets on the market capitalization of quoted consumer goods companies in Nigeria?
- iv. What is the combined influence of tangible assets, intangible assets, and current assets on the market capitalization of quoted consumer goods companies in Nigeria?

Hypotheses of the Study

The hypotheses of the study were formulated from the objectives and are stated in null forms:

- H01:** Tangible assets do not significantly influence the market capitalization of quoted consumer goods companies in Nigeria.
- H02:** Intangible assets do not significantly influence the market capitalization of quoted consumer goods companies in Nigeria.
- H03:** Current assets do not significantly influence the market capitalization of quoted consumer goods companies in Nigeria.
- H04:** Tangible assets, intangible assets, and current assets have no combined influence on the market capitalization of quoted consumer goods companies in Nigeria.

Conceptual Review

The relevant variables associated with asset structure and market value were reviewed accordingly in line with the view of scholars in accounting.

Market Value

Market value could be described as the worth regarding assets, equity, and debts of quoted companies at a given period of time (Uzliawati et al., 2018). It is the worth of basic accounting attributes because they are often regarded as what could be obtained from the markets at a given period (Almahadin & Oroud, 2019). Based on this definition, it could be said that there are market values of assets, equity, and debt, and in this case, market value itself depends on the proxy used at a time and is not specific in nature. The most acceptable method of assessing the market value of assets is by comparing the exact carrying amount of the assets as reported on the statement of financial position with the recoverable amount in the markets for the assets. The recoverable amount is often determined by selecting the higher of the value in use or the fair value of the assets less the cost to sell (Melville, 2014). Value in use is regarded as the present value of future cash flows discounted with an acceptable rate. When the recoverable amount of assets is higher than the carrying amount reported on the statement of financial position of quoted companies, it means there is no impairment. On the other hand, when the recoverable amount is less than the carrying amount, it means there is impairment loss, and in such a situation, the book value of the assets should be adjusted for the impairment loss.

In terms of equity, market value is the worth of the total equity of a quoted company at a given period (Data et al., 2017). Market value of equity is the focus of this study as the dependent variable. It focuses on market capitalization, price-to-earnings (P/E) ratio, price-to-book ratio, Tobin's Q, and others (Fumani & Moghadam, 2015). In terms of debt, market value is the current value of debt based on the level of interest rate fixed by the financial markets (Iskandar, 2021). In terms

of debt, market value depends on the fluctuation in the interest rate in the financial markets of any economy (Abughniem et al., 2021).

Measurement of Market Value

The key measurements of market value are reviewed accordingly (Setiadharna & Machali, 2017) are:

- i. The market price of shares:** This is the value of a unit of shares in the stock market based on the company's performance or reputation achieved. When the price of shares decreases, the wealth of shareholders is usually affected adversely, and when the price of shares rises, the wealth of shareholders increases (Nyamasege et al., 2014).
- ii. Market Capitalization:** Market capitalization is calculated by multiplying the stock price by the number of equity shares outstanding (Vátavu, 2015). Market capitalization is a fundamental method in which the market value of a company can be represented. The fundamental idea behind market capitalization is that the funds of equity shareholders should grow continuously through improvement in the market price of the shares (Al-Slehat, 2020).
- iii. Price-Earnings (P/E) Ratio:** The P/E ratio is a measure of a firm's market value that is frequently used by scholars and investors to determine the worth of a company. It is determined by dividing a company's market price per share by its earnings per share (Deng and Wang, 2021). When earnings per share (EPS) exceed market price per share, the P/E ratio is less than one; when EPS is less than market price per share, the P/E ratio is greater than one (Singh & Bagga, 2019). It is common for the P/E ratio to be greater than one, indicating that earnings have a stronger impact on the market price of shares. A modest amount of earnings attracts a larger market price for a firm; an investor may regard the company as having great earning power, and as such, potential investors are frequently drawn to invest in the operation of such a company.
- iv. Tobin's Q:** Tobin's Q is a fundamental model that has been employed by modern researchers in the field of accounting and finance to measure the value of companies. In the computation of the value of companies, basic accounting attributes are usually considered, and these are debts, equity, and total assets (Iskandar, 2021). In the computation of the market value of a company, the aggregate market value of equity and debt should be compared with the market

value of total assets. In this case, the market value of equity and debt is divided by the market value of assets. The higher the ratio, the higher the market value of the company, and the lower the ratio, the lower the market value of the entity.

- v. **Market Value of Equity:** Market value of equity is recognized as a fundamental measurement of the value of companies. The basic components of equity are share capital, share premium, and retained earnings, and for the purpose of assessing the market value of equity, these components are usually aggregated and divided by the nominal value of stock quoted, multiplying the result by the market price per share. The higher the market value of equity, the higher the market value, and vice versa (Setiadharna & Machali, 2017).

Asset Structure

Asset structure is described as the possible combination of assets of quoted companies in different accounting periods. It is associated with the amount of capital contributed by either equity shareholders, debt holders, or both, which is used in the acquisition of different classifications of assets. The classifications of assets are properly made based on the expectation of managers of companies at a given accounting period. Asset structure is usually guided by the level of profits or improvement in performance indicators anticipated by managers in different accounting periods (Sinha, 2017). This simply means that for a certain amount of funds to be invested in the acquisition of a particular asset, the requirement must have been assessed by managers.

Tangible Assets and Total Assets

Tangible assets are those assets reported on the statement of financial position of an entity that could be seen, touched, or felt by any individual. A tangible asset of any quoted company is often seen as the proportion of total assets (Ramadhan et al., 2022). This simply means that the total assets accumulated by a company are often made up of tangible assets, intangible assets, and current assets. In the accumulation of total assets of a company, it is usually expected that tangible assets should have a meaningful proportion because of the role of the classes of assets in piloting the business activities of an organization (Efeeloo et al., 2020). A larger proportion of tangible assets as compared with the total assets of a company is usually expected to bring about larger revenue in different accounting periods as the proportion of the tangible assets is maintained continuously across different accounting periods.

Intangible Assets

According to IAS 38, an intangible asset is defined as an identifiable, nonmonetary asset that is without physical substance. It could be said to be an asset used by a quoted company to achieve economic benefit, but without physical form. Intangible assets could be measured by either the ratio method or the total costs method. In the ratio method, intangible assets are compared with the aggregate assets accumulated by a company. The higher the ratio, the larger the intangible assets accumulated in the accounting period, and vice versa (Dancaková et al., 2022).

Factors that Influence Market Value

These factors include company size, leverage, revenue, and age (Nyamasege et al., 2014). The factors are discussed below:

- i. Company Size:** Company size is usually calculated as the logarithm of total assets. It is an attribute that could influence the market value of quoted companies either positively or negatively. When the size of an asset is large, it shows that such a company is capable of realizing more revenue for the fact that the operation attracts more customers or investors.
- ii. Leverage:** Leverage is described as the debt capital in the capital structure of a company (Puspitasari and Wiagustini, 2019). It is also seen as the total liabilities used by a company to finance total assets that are capable of bringing about smooth operation in quoted companies (Goh et al., 2022). When a company's capital structure is highly geared, such a company is exposed to financial risk so long as interest is paid on the funds borrowed, irrespective of the rate of interest charged. A highly geared capital structure is capable of affecting the market value of quoted companies negatively, as more costs of debts are expected to be paid on the accumulated debt capital based on the agreed rate of interest.
- iii. Revenue:** Revenue is another factor that influences the market value of a company because the level of revenue generated in an accounting period usually affects other accounting attributes such as profitability, retained earnings, and dividend payments. When revenue is lowly generated, illiquidity is certain to occur as well as lower returns from investments (Sinha, 2017). Thus, revenue is a fundamental accounting attribute that could influence the market value of companies.

iv. **Age:** Age of a company is described as the duration of a period from the date of establishment or date of incorporation (Uzliawati et al., 2018). The longer the period, the better the reputation of the company's products or services in the markets. This simply means that as a company exists for a longer period of time, customers will get to know about the quality of products or services produced and the company itself will be able to hire more qualified employees, directors or managers to pilot the affairs of the organization (Puspitasari & Wiagustini, 2019). Thus, firm age is a critical attribute that could influence market value of quoted consumer goods companies in Nigeria.

Theoretical Review

Two essential theories were reviewed and considered suitable, and they are agency and signaling theories.

Agency Theory

Jensen and Meckling (1976) established and advanced this theory. The theory connects the interaction between agents and principals. The separation of ownership and management in quoted corporations allowed for the development of the theory. The potential of handing tasks to a board of directors for proper management that assures responsibility and transparency makes this management paradigm intriguing. Jensen and Meckling (1976) define agents and principals as two key participants in the theory. Agents are regarded as company board members or managers. Agents are people whose job it is to organize, direct, and control the actions of an organization in order to obtain the best possible results. The agents are individuals who are involved in the actions of piloting the affairs of the organization by devising plans and implementing such strategies to maximize rewards. In a nutshell, the agents are the company's board of directors.

Signaling Theory

Spence developed this theory in 1973 based on the perception of investors of the operation of companies. The theory, as the name implies, is concerned with giving signals to various investors and users of accounting information. This is concerned with the dependability of certain signals provided by published financial statements, as well as why other signals are irrelevant. The theory is related to the quality and reliability of accounting information provided by a company's management or directors to various users. Despite being referred to as general purpose financial information, accounting information typically published by quoted companies has a

wide range of relevance (Spence, 1973). Financial information assists some users in making effective decisions about whether or not to invest in the company. The distinctiveness in profitability declared in different accounting periods and the trend increase in revenue generated are the aspects that attract potential investors to a company, including the assets accumulated.

Signaling theory is concerned with those signs on a firm's published financial statements that entice future investors to invest in the company while also offering confidence to existing investors. Total assets, liquidity position, leverage capital, revenue, and profitability are some of the indications that prompt the curiosity of potential investors. Potential investors are frequently interested in the degree of growth in total assets shown on financial statements (Alpon et al., 2019).

Empirical Review

Almahadin and Oroud (2019) considered the capital structure-firm value nexus; The results of the analyses indicated a negative and insignificant influence of capital structure on firm value. Also, the outcome of the study showed that there was an adverse influence of debt ratio on the firm value of the studied entities.

Dharma et al. (2019) assessed the effects of profitability, growth, and size on company value with capital structure as a control variable. The results revealed that profitability showed a positive and consequential influence on firm value (FV), and capital structure had a negative influence on FV of the studied entities.

Purba and Bimantara (2019) assessed the influence of asset management on financial performance with panel data analysis. In accordance with the analysis, fixed asset turnover (FAT) exerted positive and significant influence on the financial performance of the entities studied for both models used. It was recommended that fixed asset turnover should be improved to raise more profitability for the companies.

Puspitasari and Wiagustini (2019) assessed the effect of capital structure and firm growth on firm value with profitability as a mediation variable in the Indonesian stock exchange. The result showed that capital structure and firm growth had positive and significant influence on firm value. Also, it was discovered that capital structure had a positive influence on firm value.

Ullah and Ahmad (2019) evaluated the impact of current and non-current assets on the profitability of pharmaceutical companies of Pakistan. The results showed that current assets had a positive and substantial influence on ROA, while non-current assets showed a negative and consequential influence on the ROA of the pharmaceutical entities in Pakistan studied.

Al-Slehat (2020) investigated the impact of financial leverage, size, and asset structure on firm value from the industrial sector in Jordan. The results indicated that there was a positive and significant influence of company size and leverage on company value. Hence, it was recommended that managers ensure an optimal combination of debt and equity for the long-term survival of entities.

Dinh and Pham (2020) in a study to assess the effect of capital structure on financial performance of Vietnamese listed pharmaceutical enterprises. The outcome of the analysis indicated that the long-term debt ratio and debt ratio had a positive and meaningful influence on the financial performance of the company measured by return on equity (ROE). The equity ratio was found to exert negative and significant influence on the financial performance of the entities studied. It was recommended that the entities utilize more debt capital in their operations so as to expand and spread into different markets.

Efeeloo et al. (2020) investigated the current asset management and stock performance of quoted oil and gas firms in Nigeria and concluded that efficient management of firms' current assets is capable of increasing share prices of companies. Thus, the study recommended that there should be re-evaluation of credit policies by management of oil and gas companies in order to reduce the level of the companies' receivables.

Hussein (2020) assessed the influence of capital structure on company performance in Egypt and discovered that Tobin's Q was positively and significantly influenced by short-term debt. The result also showed that long-term debt negatively influenced ROA but positively and materially influenced ROE.

Simorangkir (2020) investigated the effect of dividend payout ratio and asset growth on corporate value with the debt-to-equity ratio as a moderating variable and discovered that the dividend payout ratio had a positive and significant influence on corporate value. The result also showed that asset growth had an insignificant influence on the corporate value of the studied entities. The debt-to-equity ratio, which was the moderating variable, was found to have no effect on the relationship between asset growth and corporate value.

Abughniem et al. (2021) assessed the capital structure's effect on firms' value from a specific industry perspective in the Jordanian industrial sector as a case study. The key variables of the study were firm value proxied by earnings per share (EPS) (dependent variable) and debt divided by the total assets (DR) and the ratio of the total liability divided by total equity (DE) and the ratio of the total equity divided by total assets (EA). The sourced data were analyzed using multiple regression techniques. From the analyses conducted, it was found that DR and DE had a

negative influence on the value measured by EPS of the studied firms. Also, it was found that AE had a positive and material influence on EPS of the studied firms.

Anuar et al. (2021) ascertained the impact of non-current assets on the performance of firms in the Malaysian construction sector. The results obtained from the analyses showed that there was a positive and consequential influence of FATO on ROA and ROE of the studied entities.

Buzinskiene and Rudyte (2021) in a study to assess the impact of intangible assets on the company's market value from 2010 to 2019. From the analysis, it was observed that intangible assets showed a positive and substantial influence on the company value of the entities studied.

Iskandar (2021) examined the effect of profitability and sales growth on company value moderated by leverage. The data were analyzed using the panel regression technique, and the results showed that there was an inconsequential influence of sales growth and profitability on the value of the sampled entities.

Luu (2021) examined the impact of capital structure on firm value: The data were analyzed quantitatively using ordinary least squares (OLS), fixed-effects model (FEM), and random-effects model (REM). The result obtained from the analyses indicated that capital structure had a negative influence on the firm value of the studied entities, as the values of return on asset (ROA), asset turnover (ATO), fixed asset (FA), solvency (SOL), firm size (FSZ), and firm age (FAGE) were all negative. Thus, it was suggested in the study that managers of the studied companies should adjust their capital structure by gradually decreasing the debt ratio and also gradually increasing equity.

Shafique et al. (2021) studied the effect of asset utilization and corporate growth on financial performance. The results revealed that there was a positive and significant influence of asset utilization (AU) and corporate growth (CG) on financial performance.

Suleman and Sumani (2021) ascertained the effect of investment decision, capital structure, profitability, and company size on company value. The results showed that investment decision, profitability, and capital structure had no material influence on the firm value of the studied entities.

Temuhale and Ighoroje (2021) examined asset structure, capital structure, and performance of quoted industrial goods firms in Nigeria. The results showed that all the variables of asset structure considered in the study had a positive but insignificant influence on firm performance, while the variables of capital structure all had a positive and substantial influence on the performance of the quoted industrial goods entities in Nigeria.

Dancaková et al. (2022) investigated the impact of intangible assets on the market value of companies. From the analyses, it was found that intangible assets had a positive and substantial influence on market value. It was suggested by the researchers that investors should endeavor to assess their entities based on profitability rather than intangible asset information presented on the companies' financial statements.

Goh et al. (2022) investigated sales growth and firm size impact on firm value with ROA as a moderating variable. The results of the analyses indicated that sales growth had a negative and insignificant influence on firm value, while total assets showed a positive but insignificant influence on firm value.

Harvest et al. (2022) examined current assets, investments, and financial performance of listed industrial goods manufacturing firms in Nigeria. The independent variable of the study was current asset investment measured by inventories (INV), trade receivables (TR), and cash and cash equivalents (CCE), while the dependent variable was financial performance measured by return on assets (ROA). The results of the analyses indicated that first, INV negatively and insignificantly influenced ROA. Second, TR positively but insignificantly influenced ROA, and last, CCE positively and significantly influenced ROA. Thus, the study concluded that there was a positive and substantial relationship between current asset investment and financial performance.

Olusola et al. (2022) investigated the impact of capital structure on firm performance, using evidence from large companies in the Hong Kong Stock Exchange, and discovered that total debt had a negative and inconsequential influence on the financial performance of the studied entities.

Ramadhan et al. (2022) evaluated the impact of tangible assets and intangible assets on the value of firms listed on the index's growth. The outcome of the analysis indicated that tangible assets exerted positive and substantial influence on the firm's value, while intangible assets exerted negative and material influence on the value of the entities studied.

Charlie and Edet (2023) examined asset growth and profitability of listed manufacturing companies in Nigeria. Asset growth was measured by non-current asset growth (NCAG), current asset growth (CAG), net asset growth (NAG), and total asset growth (TAG). Profitability was measured by return on assets (ROA). From the analysis, it was observed that NCAG, NAG, and TAG exerted positive and significant influence on the profitability of manufacturing companies studied, while CAG showed positive but inconsequential influence on profitability.

Conceptual Specification of model

The Conceptual specification of model is developed by the researcher as shown in the figure below.

Independent Variables

Figure 1: Conceptual Model for the Study
 Source: Researcher's Conceptualization (2025)

Methodology

An *ex-post facto* research design involving a descriptive approach was adopted for this study. From a population of 21 quoted manufacturing firms. The entire population of the 21 companies was sampled for the study. The 20 banks were chosen because they had complete financial data for the period of the study. The type of data used in this study was regarded as panel data covering the period of 2013 to 2022.

Empirical Specification of Model

The adapted models were formulated based on the objectives of the study as presented:

$$MV_{ij} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 TANG_{ij} + \beta_2 REV_{ij} + e_t \tag{Equation 1}$$

$$MV_{ij} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 ITA_{ij} + \beta_2 REV_{ij} + e_t \tag{Equation 2}$$

$$MV_{ij} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 CA_{ij} + \beta_2 REV_{ij} + e_t \tag{Equation 3}$$

$$MV_{ij} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 TANG_{ij} + \beta_2 ITA_{ij} + \beta_3 CA_{ij} + \beta_4 REV_{ij} + e_t \tag{Equation 4}$$

where:

i=Number of companies;

j=Number of years;

β_0 =Intercept of MCAP;
 $\beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3$ and β_4 =Coefficient of each of the independent variables;
 e_t =Random error terms.
 TANG = tangible assets
 ITA = intangible assets
 CA = current assets
 MV = market value
 REV = revenue (control variable)

Descriptive Statistics

The descriptive statistics for the variables was computed and the outcomes were presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics

Statistics	MV	TANG	ITA	CA	REV
Mean	2.22E+08	67958847	15193747	49279516	1.07E+08
Median	46323001	24427791	930687.0	26982063	49970646
Maximum	3.31E+09	6.69E+08	1.51E+08	2.91E+08	8.33E+08
Minimum	766260.0	0.000000	0.000000	396133.0	297666.0
Std. Dev.	4.67E+08	1.04E+08	35197480	58494025	1.38E+08
Skewness	3.874448	3.051440	2.391247	1.817877	2.048431
Kurtosis	21.06062	14.77541	7.260404	6.231565	8.177235
Jarque-Bera	2413.946	1099.408	256.3956	147.8857	272.4252
Probability	0.000000	0.000000	0.000000	0.000000	0.000000
Sum	3.33E+10	1.02E+10	2.28E+09	7.39E+09	1.60E+10
Sum Sq. Dev.	3.25E+19	1.63E+18	1.85E+17	5.10E+17	2.82E+18
Observations	210	210	210	210	210

Source: Researcher's Computation (2025)

Test of Hypothesis One

The regression analysis was conducted in line with Market Value (MV) and Tangible Assets (TANG) as presented in Table 2.

Table 2: Fixed Effect Linear Regression Output

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	732187.1	32361566	0.022625	0.9820
TANG	3.946538	0.292608	13.48747	0.0000
REV	0.441292	0.314989	1.400977	0.1635
Effects Specification				
Cross-section fixed (dummy R-variables)				
squared	0.814721			
Adjusted R-squared	0.792431			

F-statistic	36.55216	Durbin-Watson stat	1.803082
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000000		

Dependent Variable: MV

Source: Researcher's Computation (2025)

From Table 2, Tangible Assets (TANG) had a positive and significant influence on Market Value (MV) of quoted consumer goods companies in Nigeria, while Revenue (REV) had a positive and insignificant influence on Market Value (MV) of quoted consumer goods companies in Nigeria. This result indicated that a percentage increase in TANG and REV brought about an increase in MV in quoted consumer goods companies in Nigeria. The constant value of N732,187.1 indicated the value of MV as TANG and REV were held constant and insignificant.

R² indicated that 81.47% variation in MV was attributed to the influence of TANG and REV of quoted consumer goods companies in Nigeria, and adjusted R² indicated that exactly 79.24% variation in MV was attributed to the influence of TANG of quoted consumer goods companies in Nigeria and was significant. The Durbin-Watson (DW) statistic of 1.80308 indicated that there was no first-order autocorrelation in the model. The null hypothesis, which stated that tangible assets do not significantly influence the market value of quoted consumer goods companies in Nigeria, was rejected, and the alternative hypothesis, which stated that tangible assets significantly influence the market value of quoted consumer goods companies in Nigeria, was accepted.

Test of Hypothesis Two

The regression analysis was conducted in line with Market Value (MV) and Intangible Assets (ITA) as presented in Table 3.

Table 3: Fixed Effect Linear Regression Output

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
	39204122	48693065	0.805127	0.4222
ITA	5.725194	1.609608	3.556888	0.0005
REV	2.518988	0.397759	6.332952	0.0000
Effects Specification				
Cross-section fixed (dummy variables)				
R-squared	0.599409			
Adjusted R-squared	0.551217			
F-statistic	12.43808	Durbin-Watson stat	1.512156	
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000000			

Dependent Variable: MV

Source: *Researcher’s Computation (2025)*

From Table 3, Intangible Assets (ITA) and Revenue (REV) exerted positive and significant influence on market value (MV) of quoted consumer goods companies in Nigeria. This indicated that a percentage increase in ITA and REV brought about a significant increase in MV of quoted consumer goods companies in Nigeria. The constant value of N39,204,122 indicated the value of MV as ITA and REV were held constant and insignificant.

R² indicated that 59.94% variation in MV was attributed to the influence of ITA and REV of quoted consumer goods companies in Nigeria, and adjusted R² indicated that exactly 55.12% variation in MV was attributed to the influence of ITA of quoted consumer goods companies in Nigeria and was significant. The Durbin-Watson (DW) statistic of 1.5122 indicated that there was no first-order autocorrelation in the model. The null hypothesis, which stated that intangible assets do not significantly influence the market value of quoted consumer goods companies in Nigeria, was rejected, and the alternative hypothesis, which stated that intangible assets significantly influence the market value of quoted consumer goods companies in Nigeria, was accepted.

Test of Hypothesis Three

The regression analysis was conducted in line with Market Value (MV) and Current Assets (CA) as presented in Table 4.

Table 4: Fixed Effect Linear Regression Output

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	2364464.	47611475	0.049662	0.9605
CA	3.829029	1.083664	3.533410	0.0006
REV	0.286607	0.624380	0.459026	0.6470
Effects Specification				
Cross-section fixed (dummyvariables)				
R-squared	0.598950			
Adjusted R-squared	0.550704			
F-statistic	12.41436	Durbin-Watson stat		1.840519
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000000			

Dependent Variable: MV

Source: *Researcher’s Computation (2025)*

From Table 4, Current Assets (CA) showed a positive and significant influence on the market value (MV) of quoted consumer goods companies in Nigeria, while Revenue (REV) showed a positive and insignificant influence on the market value

(MV) of quoted consumer goods companies in Nigeria. This result indicated that a percentage increase in CA and REV brought about a significant increase in MV for quoted consumer goods companies in Nigeria. The constant value of N_{2.364.464} indicated the value of MV as CA and REV were held constant and insignificant.

R² indicated that 59.89% of the variation in MV was attributed to the influence of CA and REV of quoted consumer goods companies in Nigeria, and Adjusted R² indicated that the exact 55.07% variation in MV was attributed to the influence of CA of quoted consumer goods companies in Nigeria and was significant. The Durbin-Watson (DW) statistic of 1.8405 indicated that there was no first-order autocorrelation in the model. The null hypothesis, which stated that current assets do not significantly influence the market value of quoted consumer goods companies in Nigeria, was rejected, and the alternative hypothesis, which stated that current assets significantly influence the market value of quoted consumer goods companies in Nigeria, was accepted.

Test of Hypothesis Four

The regression analysis was conducted in line with MV, TANG, ITA, and CA as presented in Table 5.

Table 5: Fixed Effect Linear Regression Output

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	28705007	31532032	0.910344	0.3643
TANG	4.005732	0.306144	13.08446	0.0000
ITA	4.357265	1.087511	4.006640	0.0001
CA	2.248367	0.799183	2.813332	0.0007
REV	0.453440	0.447070	1.014247	0.3123
Effects Specification				
Cross-section fixed (dummy variables)				
R-squared	0.835249			
Adjusted R-squared	0.812611			
F-statistic	36.89651	Durbin-Watson stat	1.771109	
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000000			

Dependent Variable: MV

Source: Researcher's Computation (2025)

From Table 5, TANG, ITA, and CA had positive and significant influence on the market value (MV) of quoted consumer goods companies in Nigeria. This result indicated that a percentage increase in TANG, ITA, CA, and REV brought about a

substantial increase in the MV for quoted consumer goods companies in Nigeria. The constant value of N28,705,007 indicated the value of MV as TANG, ITA, CA, and REV were held constant and insignificant.

R^2 indicated that 83.53% variation in MCAP was attributed to the influence of TANG, ITA, CA, and REV of quoted consumer goods companies in Nigeria, and adjusted R^2 indicated that exactly 81.26% variation in MV was attributed to the influence of TANG, ITA, and CA of quoted consumer goods companies in Nigeria and was significant. The Durbin-sWatson (DW) statistic of 1.7711 indicated that there was no first-order autocorrelation in the model. The null hypothesis, which stated that tangible assets, intangible assets, and current assets have no combined influence on the market value of quoted consumer goods companies in Nigeria, was rejected, and the alternative hypothesis, which stated that tangible assets, intangible assets, and current assets have no combined influence on the market value of quoted consumer goods companies in Nigeria, was accepted.

Discussion of the Findings

From Table 2, it was observed that the tangible assets (TANG) exerted a positive and significant influence on the market value (MV) of quoted consumer goods companies in Nigeria. This indicated that as TANG increased, MV also improved significantly. Thus, the effective use of tangible assets increased market value (MV). This study was in line with the studies of Lubyana et al. (2016) and Ramadhan et al. (2022).

From Table 3, it was observed that the intangible assets (ITA) exerted a positive and substantial influence on the market value (MV) of quoted consumer goods companies in Nigeria. This result indicated that as ITA increased, MV also improved significantly. In this case, the composition of intangible assets is expected to influence the market value of quoted companies because intangible assets are a component of non-current assets, and non-current assets have a direct influence on the revenue of quoted companies. This result simply means that when intangible assets are developed more and presented in the statement of financial position of quoted companies, it could be said that those companies have a larger market share or are recognized based on the quality of products usually produced for the market. The finding is in line with the study of Buzinskiene and Rudyte (2021) and Dancaková et al. (2022), who discovered that intangible assets exerted positive and material influence on the market value of the firms studied.

From Table 4, it was observed that Current Assets (CA) exerted a positive and material influence on the Market Value (MV) of quoted consumer goods companies in Nigeria. Thus, the influence of current assets on the market value of

quoted consumer goods companies in Nigeria clearly indicated that the level of current assets maintained was optimal and that the wealth of the shareholders was influenced positively and significantly during the period of this study. This study supported the work of Temuhale and Ighoroje (2021), who found that current assets exerted a positive, though insignificant, influence on the financial performance of the entities studied.

From Table 5, it was observed that the variables of asset structure (TANG, ITA, and CA) exerted significant influence on market value (MV) of quoted consumer goods companies in Nigeria. This means that when assets are properly structured by managers of quoted companies in terms of their composition, it is expected that the key attributes of asset structure, such as tangible assets, intangible assets, and current assets, will exert positive influence on indicators of shareholders' wealth such as market price of shares, market capitalization, and price-earnings ratio. This study was in line with the study of Nyamasege et al. (2014) and Setiadharna and Machali (2017), who found that asset structure exerted positive and material influence on firm value.

Conclusion

The study was conducted to ascertain the influence of asset structure on the market value (MV) of quoted consumer goods companies in Nigeria. The individual variables of asset structure were Tangible Assets (TA), Intangible Assets (ITA), and Current Assets (CA). Revenue (REV) was chosen by the researcher as a control variable to reduce the spuriousness of the empirical results in the individual model. From the analyses, it was concluded that asset structure had a significant influence on the Market Value (MV) of quoted consumer goods companies in Nigeria. Individually, Tangible Assets (TANG), Intangible Assets (ITA), and Current Assets (CA) had a positive and significant influence on the Market Value (MV) of quoted consumer goods companies in Nigeria, where intangible assets exerted the highest influence on the market value.

Recommendations

Based on the empirical results obtained, the following recommendations were made:

- i. Property, plant, and equipment of the quoted consumer goods companies in Nigeria should be acquired and accumulated for the purpose of generating more revenue and profitability of the companies.

- ii. Quoted consumer goods companies in Nigeria should invest more in acquiring tangible assets like investment properties to raise the wealth of the shareholders.
- iii. The development costs of quoted consumer goods companies in Nigeria that meet the criteria of recognizing them as intangible assets should be capitalized and presented on statements of financial position of those entities.
- iv. Current assets accumulated by quoted consumer goods companies in Nigeria should be managed effectively continuously to ensure that the liquidity position of the entities is not affected negatively.
- v. Adequate investment and effective management should be done on the key variables of asset structure, such as tangible, intangible, and current assets, for the purpose of influencing increased market value.

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